

Social Engineering Attacks: Global Trends, Nigerian Case Studies, and Mitigation Strategies

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Article History:

Received: 18.10.2025 Revised: 29.10.2025 Accepted: 30.10.2025 Published: 31.10.2025

ABSTRACT:

Social engineering involves the psychological manipulation of individuals to obtain confidential information or induce them to perform actions that compromise security. Despite growing investments in cybersecurity infrastructure, human vulnerability remains the weakest link in digital defense systems, enabling attackers to bypass technical safeguards through deception. This paper examines the dynamics of social engineering attacks, highlighting global trends, Nigerian case studies, and key mitigation strategies. Drawing on secondary data from fraud reports and documented incidents, the study observes a notable shift from technical exploits to human-targeted deception techniques such as phishing, smishing, and impersonation. The Nigerian cases, particularly those involving political and financial fraud, mirror global patterns in both method and motivation. Findings indicate that social engineering remains one of the most pervasive and costly forms of cybercrime, primarily due to its exploitation of human error and trust. The study recommends sustained public awareness campaigns, stronger identity verification protocols, multi-factor authentication, and behaviour-based training as critical measures for mitigating these threats and enhancing digital security resilience.

Keywords: Social Engineering, Phishing Attack, Cybercrime, Human vulnerabilities, Cybersecurity.

Suggested Citation: O.Z. Apene, N.E. Akpowowo, A.E. Salihu, O.K. Okome, O.G. Mega, J.E. Ikikiru, "Social Engineering Attacks: Global Trends, Nigerian Case Studies, and Mitigation Strategies," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(5), pp. 241-249, Sep-Oct 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(5).20

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INTRODUCTION

In today's digitally interconnected world, the threat landscape is no longer limited to technical exploits but also encompasses the manipulation of human psychology. Social engineering has emerged as a formidable and often underestimated threat to information security [1]. As organizations continue to expand, safeguarding data, privacy, and digital assets has become a critical concern. While significant investments are made in hardware and software security solutions, research shows that the greatest vulnerability often lies not in technological weaknesses such as malware, unpatched software, or poorly configured firewalls, but in human behaviour itself [2].

The persistence and universality of social engineering threats stem from the inevitability of human involvement in computer systems. Regardless of how advanced or well-implemented security measures may be, humans remain susceptible to manipulation, making this weakness both platform-independent and persistent across technologies [3]. Social networking platforms, in particular, present fertile ground for such attacks. With billions of users sharing personal and sensitive information, these networks have become prime targets for social engineering exploits [4].

In Nigeria, for example, social engineering attacks are widespread, taking the form of deceptive text messages, fraudulent WhatsApp communications, and impersonation through phone calls, amongst others. Despite growing academic and industry research in this area, both individuals and organizations remain highly vulnerable. The rapid proliferation of social media platforms has also intensified the risks. Recognizing that humans are the weakest link in any security system, this paper provides a review of social engineering attacks. Specifically, it examines the types of attacks, emerging global and Nigerian trends, and the strategies to mitigate their impact.

Concept of Social Engineering

Social engineering is recognized as a significant organizational threat, often initiated by human agents who exploit user behaviour. Such attacks, also referred to as human hacking, manifest in different forms but are most frequently delivered through mobile devices in the form of electronic messages, including voice calls, texts, images, and videos. Phishing remains the most common example. The effectiveness of these attacks largely depends on the victim's susceptibility to trust, which allows intruders to gain access to sensitive information that can later be weaponized against the organization [2].

Social engineering is the practice of manipulating individuals to disclose confidential data such as login credentials, home addresses, and financial details by exploiting inherent human vulnerabilities. Instead of targeting technical flaws, these attacks capitalize on psychological factors such as trust, fear, emotions, or habitual behaviour to deceive individuals into sharing information [5].

According to [6], social engineering occurs when attackers manipulate individuals into taking certain actions or revealing sensitive and personal information. The data provided by victims is then used in deceptive ways that strengthen the attacker's scheme. In this context, social engineering relies on exploiting the trust that people place in digital communications, where the victim's unintentional cooperation enables the attacker to execute their plan.

Based on the foregoing, social engineering can be defined as the act of maliciously manipulating or deceiving individuals into revealing sensitive information, granting unauthorized access, or performing actions that compromise security. Unlike purely technical exploits, social engineering primarily leverages psychological manipulation rather than technological vulnerabilities. Attackers exploit trust, fear, curiosity, or urgency to influence human behaviour. Although social engineering is often categorized into various types, including non-technical (psychological manipulation) and technical (phishing, malware delivery, or spoofed websites), its foundation lies in exploiting human weaknesses rather than flaws in hardware or software.

In essence, social engineering is the deliberate use of psychological manipulation to deceive individuals into disclosing sensitive information, granting unauthorized access, or performing actions that compromise security. While it may sometimes involve technical tools, its foundation lies more in exploiting human behaviour than in exploiting technological weaknesses.

Forms of Social Engineering Attacks

Social engineering attacks are widespread in both developed and developing countries and remain a common form of exploitation. Because many such attacks rely on human manipulation rather than technical complexity, they often require less effort than brute-force or purely technical attacks (for example, repeatedly guessing passwords). Consequently, social engineering, especially phishing and its variants, continues to grow in prevalence. Common forms include phishing, spear phishing, pretexting, vishing/smishing, baiting, BEC (Business Email Compromise), quid pro quo, tailgating, scareware, as well as romance scams and fake investment or cryptocurrency schemes [1].

[7] provides a simple illustrative scenario of a social engineering incident. An attacker researches an organization and learns that a help-desk employee knows the wireless network password. After collecting personal details about the employee, the attacker poses as a former school acquaintance to establish rapport. Having gained the employee's trust, the attacker requests use of the company Wi-Fi "just to send an email," thereby obtaining network access under false pretenses.

From this example, the core stages of many social engineering attacks can be summarized as four distinct steps:

1. **Reconnaissance and Target Identification.** The attacker gathers information about the organization and identifies an individual whose role or knowledge grants useful access (for example, a help-desk staffer who knows the wireless password).
2. **Pretext Development.** Using the collected personal details, the attacker fabricates a believable persona or story (the "old school acquaintance") to justify contact and foster credibility.
3. **Trust Exploitation.** The attacker leverages the established rapport and psychological triggers to persuade the target to perform a seemingly innocuous action.
4. **Security Bypass and Access.** The victim's cooperation allows the attacker to circumvent technical controls and gain unauthorized access to systems or data.

These stages align with the framework of Algarni et al. (2013) -change to IEEE, who identified four key entities shaping social engineering on social networking sites: the platform (environment), the attacker (social engineer), the trick (plan and technique), and the victims (SNS users). Figure 1 shows the different stages of social engineering.

Figure 1. Stages of Social Engineering Attack

Figure 2. The Four-Entity Model of Social Engineering Attacks on Social Networking Sites

Figure 2 illustrates social engineering on SNS as a cyclical process involving four entities: the attacker (social engineer), the trick (plan and technique, such as phishing or pretexting), the environment (social networking platform), and the victims (SNS users) whose trust is exploited. The circular flow shows how the attacker deploys the trick through the platform, with the victim's compromised action completing the attack, highlighting that such exploits target human psychology rather than technical vulnerabilities.

Global Case studies of Social Engineering Attacks

According to [8], phishing (T1566) delivered through attachments, links, or phishing as a service remained the leading initial infection vector, accounting for 41% of all incidents remediated in 2022. This report was consistent with 2021, following an increase from 33% in 2020. Among phishing incidents, spear phishing via attachments (T1566.001) represented 62% of cases, spear phishing links (T1566.002) 33%, and phishing as a service (T1566.003) 5%, with some attacks combining attachments with phishing services or malicious links. Data from IBM X-Force Red in 2022 further highlights the central role of phishing and credential misuse, revealing that approximately 54% of penetration tests showed weaknesses in authentication or credential handling. The X-Force Red Adversary Simulation team also observed spear phishing campaigns using QR codes to compromise multifactor authentication tokens, while many organizations lacked sufficient visibility into applications and endpoints exposed through identity and access management systems and single sign-on platforms such as Okta.

In 2023, the Cofense Phishing Detection and Response Platform, powered by over 35 million trained employees, detected a record surge in malicious emails bypassing Secure Email Gateways (SEGs), highlighting a 37% increase from 2022 and a 310% rise since 2021, with attacks occurring every 57 seconds on average. This alarming trend emphasizes that social engineering remains a critical and evolving tool for cybercriminals to breach security, as traditional email defenses increasingly fail against sophisticated tactics like vishing, smishing, brand impersonation, and QR code phishing, which saw a 331% rise in threat reports. Targeting primarily healthcare and finance sectors where malicious bypasses grew by 84.5% and 118% respectively attackers exploit human vulnerabilities to steal credentials and deploy new malware such as DarkGate and PikaBot. The Cofense report stresses that because 90% of data breaches originate from phishing attacks aimed at employees, organizations cannot rely on "good enough" security and must adopt more dynamic solutions to counter these advanced social engineering threats effectively [9].

According to [10] in SecurityWeek reports, threat actors have been targeting IT help desk staff at healthcare and public health organizations by impersonating financial employees to fraudulently enroll new devices into multi-factor authentication (MFA). Using stolen personal details, attackers convinced staff to bypass security, gained access to networks, located payer login credentials, altered Automated Clearing House (ACH) payment accounts, and diverted funds through U.S. banks to overseas accounts. While similar social engineering tactics were previously observed in a 2023 ransomware attack linked to Scattered Spider, the recent incidents did not deploy ransomware.

In September 2025, PyPI disclosed a phishing campaign that exemplifies the growing sophistication of social engineering attacks against open-source ecosystems. The campaign involved emails crafted to look like official communications, warning users that their accounts could be suspended unless they verified their credentials. Victims who clicked on the embedded link were redirected to "pypi-mirror.org", a fraudulent domain not associated with PyPI or the Python Software Foundation. This tactic mirrors earlier phishing incidents targeting PyPI and other open-source repositories, with attackers continually registering new domains to evade detection [15]. The case highlights the severity of social engineering threats, which exploit user trust and urgency to obtain sensitive information.

Fraud Analysis by Technique in Nigeria (2022–2023)

According to the [11] annual fraud report, fraud in Nigeria continues to evolve, with threat actors adopting diverse techniques to exploit individuals and financial institutions. Fig. 3 presents a breakdown of reported fraud cases and associated financial losses across different attack methods for 2022 and 2023.

Figure 3(a). Reported Fraud Cases in Nigeria (2022-2023)

Figure 3(b). Reported Fraud Losses in Nigeria (2022- 2023)

Source: [11]

The data in Figures 3(a) and 3(b) reveals that social engineering remains the most prevalent and damaging fraud method, recording tens of thousands of cases annually and billions of naira in financial losses. Although its reported cases declined slightly in 2023, the loss value remained extremely high compared to other fraud types. Techniques such as phishing and SMSHING also showed growth but still fall under the broader social engineering category. In contrast, traditional fraud methods like PIN compromise, card theft, and phone theft accounted for significant numbers of cases but resulted in relatively lower financial losses. The figures confirm a shift towards psychological manipulation as the dominant fraud vector in Nigeria

Recent Nigerian Case of Social Engineering Attack (2024)

In 2024, The Guardian [12] reported that the Akwa Ibom State Government confirmed the compromise of Governor Umo Eno's WhatsApp account by cybercriminals who cloned his phone number to send fraudulent messages soliciting money transfers with promises of reimbursement. According to the governor's Chief Press Secretary, Ekerete Udoh, the public was urged to disregard such messages as law enforcement agencies commenced investigations. This incident came shortly after a similar breach involving Osun State Governor Ademola Adeleke, highlighting the growing prevalence of social engineering and digital impersonation attacks targeting high-profile individuals in Nigeria.

Similarly, in December 2024, Nigeria's Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) uncovered a large-scale international syndicate engaged in cryptocurrency investment and romance scams, leading to the arrest of 792 suspects, including several foreign nationals from China, the Philippines, and other countries. The operation exposed a network where foreign actors trained Nigerian accomplices to conduct phishing, create fake profiles, and execute online scams targeting victims globally. Nigerian agents initiated contact through romantic and investment schemes on social media, directing victims to fraudulent platforms before foreign collaborators completed the deception and absconded with the funds. Numerous arrests and asset seizures were made, underscoring both the magnitude and transnational dimension of the crime [13]. Collectively, these cases exemplify the expanding scope of social engineering in Nigeria, where manipulation and psychological deception continue to be powerful tools for committing financial and digital fraud.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Social Engineering Comparison with other Fraud Types

As indicated in the [11] report, traditional fraud methods, such as PIN compromise, card theft, and phone theft, collectively accounted for thousands of cases but resulted in relatively lower financial losses, typically ranging from hundreds of millions to just over ₦1 billion. In contrast, social engineering, including phishing, SMSing, generated losses exceeding ₦8 billion in 2023 alone. This clear disparity suggests that Nigerian threat actors increasingly rely on psychological manipulation rather than technical exploits, as it requires fewer resources and more easily circumvents conventional security mechanisms.

Shift in Attack Trends

The data indicate a continued shift from brute-force or physically intensive fraud, such as card theft and robbery, toward deception-based strategies. While card-related fraud remains notable, its associated financial losses either declined or slightly increased. Meanwhile, social engineering, including phishing, SMSing, and impersonation attacks, has grown in both frequency and financial impact. Recent incidents in 2024, including the compromise of state governors' WhatsApp accounts and the large-scale cryptocurrency and romance scam uncovered by the EFCC, reflect this trend toward more sophisticated and socially engineered schemes. These attacks increasingly exploit personal data, social media, and communication platforms to manipulate victims through trust, authority, or emotional appeal.

Implications for Nigeria

The persistence, adaptability, and financial toll of social engineering reveal its deep entrenchment in Nigeria's cybercrime ecosystem. Criminals exploit human vulnerabilities, particularly trust and a sense of urgency, to deceive individuals and even high-profile officials into disclosing confidential information or authorizing fraudulent transactions. The rise of impersonation attacks targeting public figures shows the large scope of these threats beyond traditional banking fraud. Consequently, there is an urgent need for intensified cybersecurity awareness campaigns, continuous digital literacy programs, and stronger authentication protocols within both the public and private sectors. Without such measures, social engineering will continue to evolve as the most damaging and resilient form of cyber-enabled fraud in Nigeria.

Global and Nigerian Parallels

The Nigerian experience aligns closely with global patterns identified by IBM, Cofense, and PyPI, where phishing, credential theft, and impersonation dominate as leading attack vectors. Internationally, attackers exploit corporate email systems, open-source repositories, and online platforms, while in Nigeria, similar manipulation tactics drive financial fraud and political impersonation. Both contexts demonstrate that attackers now prioritize human weaknesses over technical vulnerabilities, with innovative approaches such as QR code phishing, social media cloning, and identity spoofing becoming common. This convergence shows that social engineering is not only a Nigerian problem but a global cybersecurity challenge rooted in human psychology and the exploitation of trust.

Social Engineering Mitigation Strategies

According to the Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System (NIBSS), mitigating social engineering fraud requires both customer awareness and institutional safeguards. Banks should educate customers to promptly report suspicious messages or calls, avoid sharing sensitive information, and enable SIM and phone locks to prevent phone theft fraud. Institutions should also deploy strong email filters to detect malicious content and implement multi-factor authentication (MFA) to enhance account security and prevent unauthorized access.

Furthermore, to address social engineering threats targeting IT help desk employees in healthcare and public health (HPH) organizations, [14] recommended implementing verification procedures such as callback confirmation to an employee's registered phone number for new device enrollments

or password resets, continuous monitoring for suspicious Automated Clearing House (ACH) modifications, and requiring supervisory authorization for all high-risk requests.

In addition, effective mitigation of social engineering threats begins with education and awareness, enabling individuals and organizations to understand common manipulation tactics and recognize warning signs. All requests for sensitive information should be verified through official communication channels. Strong authentication measures, including unique passwords, two-factor authentication, and regular software updates, should be implemented. Continuous cybersecurity training also helps employees identify and respond to potential attacks effectively, aligning with the suggestions of [1].

Moreover, to minimize risks across social media and digital platforms, users must remain vigilant and consistently apply strong security practices. Enabling Two-Factor Verification (2FA) on platforms such as WhatsApp is an essential step in preventing unauthorized account access. In line with global cybersecurity best practices, users should never open or click suspicious links or attachments received through digital channels such as WhatsApp, Facebook, email, or text messages. Likewise, individuals should refrain from responding hastily to unknown callers requesting personal, financial, or sensitive information. If a caller claims to represent an organization and requests verification codes sent to the user for a supposed meeting or activity, such claims must be independently verified through official and trusted communication channels. Threat actors frequently exploit human vulnerabilities by creating a false sense of urgency to induce quick and uninformed decisions. Therefore, users are advised to remain calm, think critically, and carefully evaluate any unexpected requests before responding. Adopting these cautious practices can significantly reduce the likelihood of falling victim to social engineering attacks.

Figure 4 presents a summary of six fundamental defense strategies designed to mitigate social engineering attacks. These strategies emphasize both individual awareness and institutional safeguards, outlining key preventive measures for reducing vulnerability to manipulation-based threats.

Figure 4. Fundamental Social Engineering Mitigation Strategies

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This study examined social engineering attacks as a significant and evolving cyber threat that exploits human psychology rather than system vulnerabilities. It was established that social engineering remains one of the most prevalent forms of cybercrime globally and in Nigeria, where

attackers manipulate users' trust through tactics such as phishing, pretexting, and baiting. The findings show that the success of these attacks relies largely on the attacker's ability to craft persuasive narratives, exploit personal data, and manipulate digital communication channels.

The study highlights that effective mitigation requires a multi-layered defense strategy that integrates both technical and human-centered interventions. Recommended measures include continuous cybersecurity awareness training, multi-factor authentication, robust email filtering systems, and strict identity verification protocols. Cultivating a culture of critical thinking, caution, and digital vigilance among users is equally vital in minimizing human error and manipulation. Although this study relied on secondary data, future research will incorporate primary data collection to better assess individuals' exposure to social engineering across varied contexts and examine the psychological and behavioural factors influencing susceptibility. Furthermore, as Generative AI (GenAI) continues to evolve, subsequent studies should investigate its role in enabling social engineering attacks and develop corresponding Artificial Intelligence (AI) -based defense strategies.

Ultimately, combating social engineering requires not only technological advancement but also a sustained investment in human awareness and behavioural resilience. Strengthening the human firewall remains the most critical step toward ensuring a secure and trustworthy digital ecosystem.

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